

Asymmetric q-Gaussian functions to fit the Raman LO mode band in Silicon Carbide

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Abstract

Previous studies (Sparavigna, 2023) have demonstrated the Tsallis q-Gaussian functions suitable for the analysis of Raman spectra. The q-Gaussians are symmetric functions that can be used for simulating different line shapes of Raman bands. Here we use two asymmetric forms of the q-Gaussians, to fit the Raman LO mode band of Silicon Carbide. The first form considered is the generalization of the Breit-Wigner-Fano function, the other is made by two different half q-Gaussians, used for fitting the two sides of the peak.

Keywords: Tsallis q-Gaussian distribution, asymmetric q-Gaussian distribution, Gaussian distribution, Cauchy distribution, Lorentzian distribution, Raman spectroscopy.

q-Gaussian functions, also known as "Tsallis functions", are probability distributions derived from the Tsallis statistics (Tsallis, 1988, 1995, Hanel et al., 2009). The q-Gaussians are based on a generalized form of the exponential function (see discussion in Sparavigna, 2022), characterized by a continuous parameter q in the range $1 < q < 3$. As given by Umarov et al., 2008, the q-Gaussian function is based on function $f(x) = C e_q(-\beta x^2)$, where $e_q(\cdot)$ is the q-exponential function and C a constant. In the exponent, we use $\beta = 1/(2\sigma^2)$, with variance σ . The q-exponential has expression: $exp_q(u) = [1 + (1 - q)u]^{1/(1-q)}$, which possesses a bell-shaped profile. In the case that we have the peak of the function at position x_o , the q-Gaussian function is given as:

$$q\text{-Gaussian} = C exp_q(-\beta(x - x_o)^2) = C [1 - (1 - q)\beta(x - x_o)^2]^{1/(1-q)}$$

For q equal to 2, the q-Gaussian is the Cauchy-Lorentzian distribution (Naudts, 2009). For q close to 1, we have the usual Gaussian form. For the q -parameter between 1 and 2, the shape of the q-Gaussian function is intermediate between the Gaussian and the Lorentzian profile. This behavior turns the q-Gaussian into a function suitable for the analysis of Raman spectra, where the spectral bands are characterized, in the same manner, by intermediate profiles between Lorentzian and Gaussian outlines (Kirillov, 2004a). Besides these two functions, which remain the most popular for fitting Raman spectra, *linear combinations* (pseudo-Voigt distributions) or *convolutions* of them (Voigt distributions) are used too (Meier, 2005). The Voigtian function is essentially a Lorentzian height weighted by a Gaussian profile.

Gaussian, Lorentzian, Voigtian and pseudo-Voigtian functions, such as the q-Gaussians are symmetric functions. In fitting the Raman bands, we have encountered peaks which are asymmetric. For instance, in the case of Diamond, (see [SSRN](#)), we had the necessity to use three q-Gaussians to fit the asymmetric

Raman peak of the spectrum of synthetic diamond. Of course, the presence of more bands producing what looks like an asymmetric peak can be motivated by physical reasons; in any case, alternative approaches can be used to fit asymmetric profiles. A possibility is that of using Breit-Wigner-Fano (BWF) functions or Voigt asymmetric functions, however another form of asymmetric q-Gaussian exists, like that the asymmetric form of Tsallis distribution has been used by S. Devi, 2021, for modeling the financial market dynamics. The form is made by two different half q-Gaussians, used for fitting the two sides of the peak.

Here we consider some cases, in particular the Raman LO mode of Silicon Carbide. Let us start from the BWF function.

q-BWF function

The Breit-Wigner-Fano function is given as:

$$BWF = C \frac{[1 + \xi \gamma^{1/2}(x - x_o)]^2}{[1 + \gamma(x - x_o)^2]}$$

In it, ξ is the asymmetry parameter (see Hasdeo et al., 2014, for the use of Breit-Wigner-Fano line shapes for the Raman spectrum of graphene). We could generalize the BWF in the q-form (BFW_q):

$$q\text{-BWF} = C [1 + \xi \beta^{1/2}(q - 1)^{1/2}(x - x_o)]^2 [1 + (q - 1)\beta(x - x_o)^2]^{1/(1-q)}$$

However, we can further generalize the asymmetric form in the following manner:

$$q\text{-BWF} = C [1 + \xi \beta^{1/2}(q - 1)^{1/2}(x - x_o)]^{2\alpha} [1 + (q - 1)\beta(x - x_o)^2]^{1/(1-q)}$$

When $q=2$, $\alpha=1$, we have the function BWF.

Hasdeo and coworkers are giving, in their Eq.(1), the BWF line shape composed by three terms: “a constant continuum spectrum, a discrete Lorentzian spectrum, and an interference effect between both spectra”. The interference term is producing the asymmetry of the profile, according to the positive and negative values of the argument $(x-x_o)$. The dimensionless ξ parameter is “mimicking the ratio between the probability amplitude of the continuum spectra to that of the discrete spectra” (Hasdeo et al., 2014). Also in Praver and Nemanich, 2004, we can find mentioned the asymmetry of Raman peaks according to specific effects; we find also the “phonon confinement effects for finite crystal domains” (Richter et al., 1981). In Campbell and Fauchet, 1986, we can easily see that the effects of microcrystal size on the shape of Raman spectra. In their Fig.4, an asymmetric peak for thin film of silicon on sapphire (SOS) is shown.

Let us start from fitting with q-BWF the curve proposed in the Fig.3(a) by Hasdeo et al. The continuous curve is given by Hasdeo and coworkers according to a theoretical model. The curve is clearly asymmetric. The fitting result is shown in the following Figure. We can see that the q-BWF is a BWF function, as expected by the theory.

Fig. 1: The best fit (blue) onto the curve (red) given by Hasdeo et al. A q -BWF is used (the values of α , ξ and q -parameters are given in the figure). The misfit is proposed in the lower part of the plot. On the right, the same fit is shown with the log scale for y -axis (semi log scale). Data and q -BWF are given as functions of integers n (equally spaced points), for the x -axis which is representing the Raman shift. A convenient scale is used for the y -axis (intensity axis). The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=660$). The value of this sum is 5.5×10^{-5} .

Let us consider the work by Campbell and Fauchet, 1986, and their Fig.4, with the peak for thin film of silicon on sapphire (SOS).

Fig. 2: The best fit (blue) onto the curve (red) given by Campbell and Fauchet, 1986. A q -BWF is used (the values of α , ξ and q -parameters are given in the figure). The misfit is proposed in the lower part of the plot. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=230$). The value of this sum is 8.5×10^{-4} .

Then, let us try to apply the q -BWF to a specific case, that of the LO mode Raman band, regarding a material which possesses remarkable properties, such as a high thermal conductivity, the Silicon Carbide. Data are obtained from the Raman Open Database, a database which developed in the framework of project SOLSA H2020 (El Mendili et al., 2019),

<https://solsa.crystallography.net/rod/1000172.html> . In the file, it is told that the Raman spectrum is related to a 6H-SiC structure, sample from a terrestrial moissanite, locality at 150 km NW from Izmir, Turkey. About the moissanite and the LO mode in SiC see please Chafai et al., 2001, Rashid et al., 2016, Koyanagi et al., 2016, Liu et al., 2010, Xu et al., 2008, Kiefert et al., 2002, and Shiryaev et al., 2011.

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Fig.3: The best fit (blue) onto data (red) of ROD 1000172 (related ref. Capitani et al., 2007). On the right, the data with log scale y-axis (semi log scale). A q-BWF is used (the values of parameters are given in the figure). The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=660$). The value of this sum is 6.6×10^{-4} .

The fit is rather good. However, it seems that the peak has a left shoulder; moreover, the left wing is not properly fitting the data, as we can easily see in the semi log scale. So let us consider fitting this peak with symmetric Gaussians.

Symmetric Gaussians for LO mode SiC

In the following plots, the fits by means of symmetric q -Gaussians are shown for LO mode in SiC.

Fig.4: The best fit (magenta) onto data (red) of ROD 1000172 (related ref. Capitani et al., 2007). A symmetric q -Gaussian is used. The sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=660$) is equal to 1.82×10^{-3} .

Fig.5: The best fit (green) onto data (red) of ROD 1000172 (related ref. Capitani et al., 2007). Two symmetric q -Gaussians are used (magenta, blue). The sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=660$) is equal to 2.94×10^{-5} .

In the Figure 5, we have a good fit, however it is posing a question. We have two components with the same approximate high. This is suggesting that we are facing a fit which needs further tests. Let us add a third component (Fig.6) on the left, and a further component (Fig.7) on the right.

Fig.6: The best fit (green) onto data (red) of ROD 1000172 (related ref. Capitani et al., 2007). Three symmetric q -Gaussian have been used. The sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=660$) is equal to 1.25×10^{-5} .

Fig.7: The best fit (green) onto data (red) of ROD 1000172 (related ref. Capitani et al., 2007). Four symmetric q -Gaussian have been used. The sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=660$) is equal to 6.8×10^{-6} .

Asymmetric Tsallis line

Figures 6 and 7 are evidencing that we can have a main band (made of two components) with a relevant shoulder on the left. This suggest us to try to use an asymmetric q -Gaussian, in the simple form as in Devi, 2021, that is:

$$q\text{-Gaussian}_{\text{LEFT}} = C \exp_{q_L}(-\beta_L(x - x_o)^2) = C[1 - (1 - q_L)\beta(x - x_o)^2]^{1/(1-q_L)},$$

when $x - x_o < 0$

$$q\text{-Gaussian}_{\text{RIGHT}} = C \exp_{q_R}(-\beta_R(x - x_o)^2) = C[1 - (1 - q_R)\beta_R(x - x_o)^2]^{1/(1-q_R)},$$

when $x - x_o > 0$

Parameters q and β of the two half parts are different. Here the resulting plots with one and two asymmetric q -Gaussians.

Fig.8: The best fit (blue) onto data (red) of ROD 1000172 (related ref. Capitani et al., 2007). An asymmetric q -Gaussian has been used. The sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=660$) is equal to 2.9×10^{-4} .

Fig.9: The best fit (green) onto data (red) of ROD 1000172 (related ref. Capitani et al., 2007). An asymmetric (blue) q -Gaussian have been used and a q -Gaussian (magenta). The sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=660$) is equal to 1.55×10^{-5} .

The results proposed in the two previous plots, regarding the case of the LO mode of SiC are really encouraging for applying the asymmetric q-Gaussian to fitting the bands of the Raman spectrum.

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